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Towards Unveiling Challenges of Pastoral Ministry in Nigeria and Some Strategies for Its Improvement

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Abstract

Pastoral ministry in Nigeria faces a lot of untold challenges that hinders its effectiveness in addressing the spiritual and social needs of the congregants. This study explores the multifaceted obstacles encountered by pastors, including socio-economic constraints, political instability, inter-religious conflicts, and inadequate training. This study employs a qualitative ethnographic methodology with data collection through in-depth interviews in Egbeda local government Area of Oyo State where there are about three hundred Churches. Twenty people were interviewed, and they are pastors, elders, and youth members of the church each. The theoretical framework for this research is the Transformational Leadership theory which focuses on leadership dynamics and strategies for improvement in pastoral ministry in Nigeria. Despite the growing population of Christians, many pastors' struggles with limited resources and support systems, this affects and poses big threats to their ability to provide holistic ministry. Furthermore, the rise of secularism and competing belief systems poses additional threats to traditional pastoral roles. The findings reveal the extent at which there should be improvement and underscore the necessities for adaptive leadership and innovative practices in the face of a rapidly changing cultural landscape, ultimately aiming to rejuvenate the church's influence and outreach in Nigerian society. The church of God needs to arise

in ameliorating the challenges to pastoral ministry else, pastoral ministry will continue to the shadow of its real purpose God wants it to be. To address these challenges, the study proposes several strategies for improvement. These includes, enhancing theological education by integrating practical ministry training, fostering collaboration among churches to share resources, and promoting community engagement initiatives that addresses local needs. Additionally, establishing mentorship programs can empower emerging leaders within the church. By implementing these strategies, pastoral ministry in Nigeria can evolve to meet contemporary demands and strengthen its role in societal transformation. The study concludes and recommends that proactiveness and charisma in the ministry can reduce the pastoral challenges in the Nigerian context.

Keywords: Pastoral Ministry, Nigerian church, Challenges, Strategies, Improvement

Introduction

Pastoral ministry is the work of shepherding God's people, involving leadership, guidance, and care. According to Mwang'ombe (2024), the term "Pastor" itself comes from the Latin word for "shepherd", highlighting the role's responsibility to lead, guide, feed, comfort, and protects the congregation by teaching and living out the word of God. it is a task given to a pastor in a ministry to guide and lead others to Christ Jesus and His ways. Pastoral ministry in Nigeria plays a vital role in shaping the spiritual, social, and moral fabric of communities across the nation. As a country with rich tapestry of religious diversity, Nigeria is home to numerous denominations and faith traditions, each contributing uniquely to the pastoral landscape. Pastoral ministry encompasses the multifaceted roles and responsibilities of a pastor or minister in providing spiritual leadership, are, and support to individuals and congregations. However, according to Anene (2022), the challenges faced by pastoral ministry are profound and multifaceted, calling for a critical examination of both the obstacles and the potential pathways for improvement. One of the most pressing issues confronting pastoral ministry in Nigeria is the increasing socio-political instability and violence that has affected many regions. The rise of extremists groups, inter-communal conflicts, and economic hardship are likely to create an environment of fear and uncertainty. Pastors and church leaders can possibly find themselves navigating complex social issues while attempting to provide spiritual guidance and support to their Congregation.

This dual role can be overwhelming, leading to burnout and reduced effectiveness in ministry.

Additionally, Awojobi (2003), postulates that the rapid urbanization and demographic shifts in Nigeria present both challenges and opportunities for pastoral ministry. As people migrate to urban area in search of better economic prospects; churches face challenges of meeting the diverse needs of a transient population. The traditional models of ministry that may have worked in rural settings often fall short in urban context, necessitating innovative approaches to outreach and community engagement.

Financial constraints also pose significant challenges to pastoral ministry in Nigeria. Many churches struggle with inadequate resources, limiting their inability to implement programs and services that address the needs of their congregations and communities. Furthermore, the reliance on donations, and tithes can create financial instability, leading to uncertainty in ministry activities and personal support. Theological education and training for pastors is another critical area that requires attention. Many church leaders according to Awojobi (2003), lack access to formal theological training, which can hinder their ability to provide sound doctrinal teaching and effective pastoral care. This gap in education can result in a lack of preparedness to address contemporary issues facing congregations, including moral dilemmas, social justice, and community development.

Despite these challenges, there are numerous opportunities for growth and improvement within pastoral ministry in Nigeria. This paper aims to explore these challenges and propose actionable strategies to enhance the effectiveness of pastoral work including the promotion of collaborative ministry practices, investment in theological education, and the integration of social justice initiatives within church programs. in the country. Fostering partnership between churches, non-governmental organizations, and community leaders, pastoral ministries can create a more holistic approach to addressing the needs of their congregation and the wider society. In the light of these aim, this study will examine how denomination leaders and stakeholders can foster a more effective and resilient ministry, contribute to the ongoing discourse surrounding pastoral ministry in Nigeria; offering insights and recommendations that can guide church leaders, and how to enhance a collaborative and innovative approach to pastoral ministries.

Moreover, leveraging technology can provide innovative solutions to some of the challenges faced by pastoral ministry. The rise of digital platforms offers new avenues for outreach, education, and community building; allowing pastors to connect with younger generations and engage with broader audience. The journey towards improving pastoral ministry in Nigeria requires a comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced by church leaders and a commitment to implementing strategic solutions.

To investigate this, the study adopts a qualitative approach that privileges thick description and contextually situated interpretation. Empirical data will be gathered through semi-structured interviews with pastors of various denominations, elders, lay-leaders, focused group discussions with at least few church members.

The aim of this study is to unravel challenges of pastoral ministry, and to dig out some of the strategies for the improvement. In pursuit of this aim, the study will examine challenges facing pastoral ministry, identify the causes of these challenges, why pastoral ministry is so important, and the strategies to adopt for its improvement. These concerns shape research questions that probe pastors and some members (elders) perceptions, of various churches selected.

An Overview of pastoral Ministry

Pastoral ministry involves a range of activities aimed at nurturing the faith, promoting spiritual growth, and attending to the overall well-being of community members. Kuruvilla (2015) said that pastoral care includes outreaches, support, counseling, and encouragement for members of the congregation.

There are key responsibilities known to the pastoral personnel. Pastoral ministry as Anene (2023) postulated is known for preaching and teaching; pastors are responsible for delivering sermons, conducting Bible studies, and offering religious education to enhance the congregation's understanding of faith and scriptures. Preaching should focus on Jesus Christ. According to Kuruvilla (2015), grasping the thrust of the text is crucial in preaching. Another key responsibility of a pastor in ministry is counseling. Providing personal and spiritual counseling to individuals dealing with various life challenges, such as grief, marital issues, or fraises of faith, is a significant aspect of pastoral ministry.

Pastor in ministry should plan and lead worship services; incorporating prayers, music, and sacrament to create a sense of community and spiritual connection. Such pastor should also engage in outreach programs, social justice initiatives, and community needs. Pastors should know how to manage the church operations, including budgeting, staff supervision, and program development, which is essential for effective ministry. Another major responsibility of a pastor as stated by Bonhoeffer (1985), is to guide individuals in their spiritual development through mentorship, discipleship, and facilitating small groups, they should be ready to be a good example for their followers or the church of God who looks up to them.

Another thing Bonhoeffer (1985) said, that should not be left out in the life of a pastor is skills and qualities to function as pastor effectively. Such skills and qualities are empathy, which will help him to understand and have compassion towards the struggles and joys of his members. Communication or vis-a-vis effective communication which is the ability to convey messages clearly both in preaching and personal interactions. Leadership skill inspires in guiding the community towards a shared vision and goal.

A greater skill mostly needed by the pastor in ministry lies in obtaining the theological knowledge that will give a deep understanding of religious texts, traditions, and doctrines. Personal holiness should also not be left out as it shows where and when true pasturing begins, describing such a pastor as a man of integrity. All these responsibilities as a pastor brings along some challenges like burnouts, crisis management and changing culture. These are necessary crises that a pastor who is effective in his ministerial life cannot but to experience in his ministerial expertise.

Pastors in the ministry that will not give room for challenges of any kind will work it out by him, or herself. For integrity sake, according to Olaleye (2011), pastor and his family should not give room for what I called 'Comparison', they should not compare themselves with other pastor in town or the one they know, if there will be peaceful experiences for their ministry in their local church. Pastor has to be careful of trying to outdo the former pastor, or making mention of it in his messages or while talking. In another development, Olaleye (2011) was of the opinion that some pastors are struggling with some problems which they are not architect of. The former pastor might have been the originator of the problems, and the people might have decided to change their policies when the former pastor left, this might have given the new pastor difficult leadership ability over the church.

The matter of comparison may become worse where the new pastor or the resident pastor does not play maturity in all matters that concerns himself, his welfare and members of his church, a lot crisis may lead to confusions. Sometimes, the comparison may even be extended to visiting pastors if the care is not well taken. This according to Olaleye (2011), means shepherding or pastoring is much more than knowing how to preach a good sermon or to teach, it involves so many things which ordinary preacher may not have or may not even need to be a successful minister in his or her ministerial activities. One elderly minister once said that, “pastors are called to be faithful and not to be successful”. This means that one of the areas pastors needs to guard jealously is their integrity in line with material possession. Pastors are expected to face their ministerial assignment and not to bother himself with material things. According to Olaleye (2011), many people still believes that any pastor that bothers himself and uses quality materials in life has already missed the mark in ministry. Kehinde (2019) underscores the meaning and significance of integrity thus: Pastoral integrity is the strength and firmness of character, or utter sincerity and honesty of a pastor as it relates to his relationships and duties in the context of the Christian faith.

Importance of Pastoral Ministry in Nigerian Context

Pastoral ministry holds significant importance in the Nigerian context, playing multifaceted roles in the lives of individuals, communities, and the nation as a whole. This stems from Nigeria’s religious landscape, characterized by a substantial Christian population alongside other faiths, and its complex socio-political environment. Anene (2013) said pastors in Nigeria serves not only as spiritual guides but also as community leaders, counselors, and agent of social change.

Among the core importance of pastoral ministry, pastoral ministry provides spiritual guidance and nurture to the congregation. Pastors leads worship services, preach messages that are rooted in biblical teachings, and offer spiritual direction to help individuals grow in their faith. In a society facing numerous challenges, including poverty, social inequality, and insecurity, the message of hope, love, and redemption offered through pastoral ministry can be particularly vital. Pastors provide a sense of meaning and purpose, helping people to navigate difficult circumstances with faith and resilience. Another thing is that pastoral counseling and support. Pastoral care extends

beyond the pulpit to offer counseling and support personal issues. Adigun & Afolaranmi (2024) remark that pastors should provide a listening ear and compassionate presence for individuals dealing with marriage problems, grief, addiction, and other challenges. In a culture where mental health services may be limited or stigmatized, pastors often serve as a first point of contact for those in need of emotional psychological support. They offer a safe space for individuals to share their burdens and receive guidance rooted in faith and biblical principles. Another importance to pastoral importance plays a crucial role in building and strengthening communities. Pastors should also foster a sense of belonging among congregants, creating opportunities for fellowship, mutual support, and collective action. According to Adigun & Afolaranmi (2024), churches in Nigeria often engage in various social welfare activities, addressing the needs of the poor, the marginalized, and the vulnerable. These activities can include providing education, healthcare, vocational training, and other essential services. By meeting the practical needs of their communities, churches demonstrate the love of Christ in tangible ways and contribute to the overall well-being of society. Awojobi (2003), opined that pastors are also expected to provide moral leadership and ethical guidance, promoting values such as honesty, integrity and social justice. In a nation grappling with corruption and other forms of moral decadence, the church has a vital role to play in shaping ethical behaviours and promoting good governance. Pastors can use their platforms to speak out against injustice, advocate for the rights of the marginalized, and inspire their congregations to live lives that reflect Christian values.

Historically, churches in Nigeria have been at the forefront of providing education and promoting literacy. Anene (2023) said mission schools played a crucial role in producing the early Nigerian elite, and churches continue to operate numerous schools and universities across the country by investing in education, churches empower individuals to improve their lives, contribute to national development, and participate more fully in the society.

Understanding Ministers/Pastors

A lot of misconceptions that people have about pastors does not allow them to know who the man (pastor) really is. The truth is that the pastor is like a masquerade to many, and only few strive to understand him and the nature

of his ministry. The man of God may be living with his own people but be in another world entirely. For anyone who relates well and tries to minister to his pastor and other pastors will understand who he is in his very nature. Olaleye (2011) talked about knowing the pastor and understand him. The first thing one need to understand about pastor is that he is a sinner saved by grace just like any other believer in the church does. He also surrendered his life to God along the way and this does not transform him to an angel immediately, he is a man that possesses flesh and blood and this can make him to still be struggling with one issue or the other in his life.

Pastors are tempted person. One thing anyone who relates with pastors needs to understand about them is that they are also facing certain temptations everyday just like any other person in the society. We need to remember David the king, as close as he was to God, as great as God demonstrated His love for him, David still fell woefully when he faced a particular temptation. Something that looked like just peeping through the window eventually landed him in a big trouble. Temptations come knocking at every door every time; the pastor's doors are not exempted. Olaleye (2011) still mention some of the things to consider when thinking about pastors, as they are human beings with a lot of weaknesses, and they are human beings with common weaknesses but at the same time, pastors are ordinary human beings with divine assignment, full of burdens in their hearts, and leaders with a lot of challenges.

Pastoral Challenges and Opportunities

Despite the importance of pastoral ministry in Nigeria, there are still numerous challenges facing the ministry. One of the major challenges is the lack of resources. Many pastors struggle with limited financial resources, which make it difficult to support their families and maintain their churches. They also face inadequate training; some pastors lack proper theological education and training, hindering their ability to effectively minister to their congregation. Sometimes, pastors face social expectations, political interference, and even persecution because of their faith. What can we say about internal challenges, pitfalls such as materialism, lack of self-control, and spiritual laziness can negatively impact pastoral ministry to a large extent. Pastors often experience psychological distress and may lack adequate mental health literacy, making it difficult to manage their own challenges and those of their congregants.

Despite these challenges, there are also significant opportunities for pastoral ministry to thrive and even make greater impact in Nigeria. These opportunities according to Anozie (2013), include:

1. ***Collaboration and partnership:*** Churches can collaborate with other organizations, including government agencies and NGOs, to address social issues and promote community development.
2. ***Empowering Congregants:*** Pastors can empower church members to take ownership of community involvement and social action, fostering a culture of service and responsibility.
3. ***Addressing Systemic Issues:*** Churches can move beyond providing immediate relief to addressing systemic issues such as poverty, corruption, and inequality.
4. ***Promoting Interfaith Dialogue:*** In a religious diverse society, pastors can play a vital role in promoting interfaith dialogue, and understanding, fostering peaceful coexistence and cooperation.
5. ***Utilizing Technology:*** Pastors can leverage technology to expand their reach, communicate with their congregations, and access resources for ministry.

With all these challenges and opportunities mentioned above, pastoral ministry is undeniably vital in the Nigerian context. According to Reken (1999), it provides spiritual guidance, emotional support, community, and moral leadership by addressing the diverse needs of individuals and communities, churches contribute significantly to the well-being of Nigerian society. Awojobi (2003) postulates that overcoming the challenges facing pastoral ministry and embracing the opportunities that exists will require a concerted efforts from pastors, church leaders, and the wider community; by working together; they should ensure that the church continues to be a transformative force for good in Nigeria.

Strategies for Improvement on Pastoral Challenges

Having discussed the challenges and opportunities about the pastoral ministry, the next is to discuss some identified strategies for the improvement on how to ameliorate those challenges. Among the strategies are:

One, there should be an improved theological training. According to Adigun and Afolaranmi (2024), Pastors should have access to quality theological education to build a solid foundation for effective ministry. Resource

provision is another thing to reduce pastoral challenges, offer more resources to rural churches, including training for pastors and church workers, and physical resources such as church buildings and equipment. If these challenges will be reduced seriously, according to them, churches should support their pastors financially, so they can devote their time to ministry without being distracted by material concerns. Anozie (2013) opined that, diversifying church income resources can also help to ameliorate the pastoral challenges.

Again, Dajur (2019), said there should be community engagement if there will be improvement. He went further to mention encouragement on community engagement, involvement in communities, and learns about their cultural practices. Self care, mental health, and emotional health of pastors should be highly prioritized; given the demanding responsibilities of their role. Other strategies identified are to mentor and be accountable, there should also be conflict resolution skills for the pastors, focusing on Biblical foundations in returning to the basic scriptural paradigm of pastoral ministry, and emphasizing biblical, theological, and ethical foundations in the church, and to the church members. To reduce the challenges, Dajur (2019), Anozie (2013), and Iwe (1979), were of opinion that pastors should give empowerment to the laity; involve them in the processes of pastoral care, working together as a team to support the church. Pastors in this age should integrate technology into pastoral practices to connect with church goers, but without undermining core values. Pastors can connect with others through online forums, webinar, and social media. The pastors should promote peace and reconciliation, as Omosor (2019) postulates that churches should emphasize teachings that promote peace, forgiveness, and reconciliation.

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive research design within a qualitative research approach to explore the effect of the pastoral challenges and strategies for improvement among some selected churches in the Christian Association of Nigeria zone 5, Egbeda local government of Oyo State. This design was chosen because it enables the researcher to study pastors' behaviours, values, and their ways of exercising ministerial activities in their various churches. It provides what Geertz (1993) called "think and description" which captures not just what they do, but the meanings they

attach to their actions. This design was considered suitable since the research topic is deeply delve into pastoral activities and behavioural within body of believer. The qualitative approach, on the other hand, allowed for the collection of rich, descriptive data, focusing on participants' lived experiences and interpretations rather than quantifiable variables. It aligns with Denzin and Lincoln's (2000) assertion that qualitative inquiry seeks to understand the world through the perspectives of those who live it, paying attention to their voices and the contextual realities in which they exist.

The targeted population of the study consisted of pastors, elders and youth members of all the sample churches of churches within the Christian Association of Nigeria, zone 5, Egbeda local government, Ibadan. These were selected because they are directly involved in the issues to research, and to find out how authentic are the findings from the pastors, and they have experiential knowledge of how the challenges would have eating deep into the fabrics of their lives and ministry. The study focused on twenty churches purposively selected across local government area. Purposive sampling was appropriate because it enabled the researcher to choose deliberately churches and participants that could provide rich and relevant data. The selection was based on prior knowledge of churches whose pastors had experienced various challenges in their ministerial lives. From these twenty churches forty participants were drawn, thirty pastors and ten members and elders in various churches.

The selected churches are: Christ Anglican Church (2), Believers Hope in Christ Church (1), Christ Apostolic Church (4), Cherubim and Seraphim (5), Baptist Church (5), Evangelical Church of Winning All – ECWA (1), Redeem Christian Church of God (2) with the number of those selected.

Data were collected primarily through semi-structured interviews, which allowed participants to express their experiences in their own words while providing the researcher with opportunities to probe deeper into emerging issues. The interview guide contained open-ended questions that explored participants' understanding of various challenges pastors face and some strategies for improvement. Each interview session lasted between twenty to thirty minutes, depending on participant's engagement. With participants' consent, all interviews were audio-recorded to ensure accuracy, while field's notes were taken to capture contextual details and non-verbal cues. In addition to interviews, participant's observation was

used during selected church meetings and activities to understand the behavioural and relational dynamics within their natural environment. The data collected were transcribed verbatim and analyzed using thematic analysis, following Braun and Clarke's iterative process of familiarization, coding, categorization, theme development, and interpretation. The researcher first read through all transcripts several times to become familiar with the data, then identify recurring ideas, phrases, and patterns. These codes were grouped into broader themes that reflected the study's objectives, including challenges that face the pastoral ministry, causes of the challenges, and how important is the pastoral ministry to the Nigerian context, and strategies for improvement. Analytical memos and reflective notes were kept throughout the process to ensure transparency and reflexivity, thereby minimizing researcher's bias.

Discussion of Findings

The first findings on this study revealed that pastors in ministry faces a lot of challenges while in active ministry. The three pastors of the Christ Apostolic Church unanimously revealed that the challenges they face ranges from the way their national leaders treat them, and even the church members. One of the serious challenges they face from time to time is that Christ Apostolic Church pastors are poorly paid, and this have led many of their colleagues to do what is not ethical to the ministry.

Many pastors in their denomination were divorced by their wives who could not endure affliction with their husbands. Some sets of Baptist pastors were interviewed and what they said was that the national body of the denomination i.e. Baptist convention fails to feel concern about how they are being remunerated in their various churches, Baptist policies does not allow the national leaders to enforce the autonomous churches pay certain amount of money that is beyond the ability of the church. In their responses, they mentioned the issue of the members being allowed to say anything in the church and especially to the pastor of the church because such person is seen as a baptized believer and the pastor must not reply nor deal with such members because he or she is a "sheep" and the ethics of the pastoral ministry does not allow such. They were all of the opinion that church members who pose issues to the pastors are the majority in the church, but the pastor has none to discuss their issues with except God. This is in line with what Olaley (2011) advised that pastors and all their household

should move away from comparison. They should not compare themselves with pastors from other denominations otherwise, they will start misbehaving.

The Pentecostal pastors (comprises of the Redeem Christian Church of God, Believers Hope in Christ Church, and some Christ Apostolic church elders which were corroborated by one prophet from cherubim and seraphim church) that were selected had a different way to address the question. They said the challenges they face was that of spiritual attacks while trying to rescue members who might be spiritually attack. They said, another area where they are having challenges is in the area of commitment of their members to the church programs, and their commitment to serve God with their resources. ECWA church pastor said that they suffer in the hand of national leaders and their members in the church. The issue of transfer of pastors to them is not fair enough and so, sometimes when they are transferred, it affects their financial lives on many occasions, and this has not given their wives ample opportunity to settle down and focuses on their businesses or their career, this means a lot to their lives and family as it affects the education of their children that are unstable. One of the respondents who is a pastor / priest in the Anglican Communion, said the priests are having challenges about the organogram of the church, too much power is in the hands of the bishop, he can just use the power anyhow, either to favour himself or show favoritism to whoever he wants. There is no one to report him to; a bishop can decide to suspend any erring priest, or he can call on him to appear before him, the answer should “yes! At your service”, he doesn’t care if such priest or pastor is engaged with something else, which means they do not live for themselves, their expectation is to obey the latest order from the bishop.

Causes of Pastoral Challenges

All respondents were of the same opinion, as they all identified the similar causes of the pastoral challenges. They all listed these as the causes of the pastoral challenges. They are:

1. Lack of effective leadership strategies
2. Lack of spiritual maturity through discipleship among the congregants
3. Pastors trivializing the issue of education

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4. Inability among the pastors to brush up their ministerial charisma through technology
 5. National leaders showing favouritisms to few sets of the pastors under them.
 6. Pastors face challenges through their personal issues. They experience burnouts, emotional issues, isolation from the congregation.

The Importance of Pastoral Ministry

The respondents were of different answers, pastors from main-line churches which were interviewed opined that the presence of pastors and their ministry in our generation makes the difference, without it, this generation would have been decayed beyond repair. They said, at least, few congregants listen to their messages and warnings and takes action afterwards; those few ones are now making impact in the society. But some church workers and members interviewed said the presence of pastors and their ministries are almost not necessary again because many of them are leading their members astray now because of the love of money. They further advised the pastors to face their calling without looking sideways, ignoring side talks, insults and slandering that un-matured members will continue to pour on them, in other to fulfill their ministry on earth.

The Christ Apostolic Church and Cherubim and Seraphim church pastors and priests, responded that the presence of pastoral work is highly necessary in our decaying world. According to their responses, they pointed out the devil and his cohorts as one of the agents to destabilize the beautiful work of God. They were of opinion that those pastors represent the presence of God, so if their ministry and presence are no more necessary, it is like we say, we don't need, or the presence of God is no more needed. Three church elders opined that the necessities of pastors and their ministries is to see the effects of their care, encouragement to the depressed souls, guiding and straightening the paths of the youth, and maintaining integrity among ladies and women in the church and community. This is exactly what Kehinde (2019) said about integrity for the pastors. Pastor, who has no integrity, has no ministry. But some youth and church workers said, the necessities of pastoral ministry cannot be over emphasized as two out of them used their lives as a testament to pastoral work of their former pastors who turned their lives to what it is today because of their effectiveness, love

and care towards the youths in the church. This corroborates Kuruvillea (2015) who said responsibilities of pastoral care include support, outreaches, counseling and encouragement of members.

Strategies for Improvement

Most of the mainline church pastors and their workers who responded to this said, some pastors especially in most of our African Independence Churches like Christ Apostolic Church are not well educated, they should give theological education a priority in this 21st century. Another respondent said, pastors should involve themselves in community engagement, building partnership with local communities, addressing local needs through outreach programs. Other pastors from Baptist and cherubim and seraphim were of the opinion that pastors who does not embrace technology this 21st century will have problem if not with the elders of the church, it will be with youth of the church, and this will eventually increase their challenges in the ministry; one of the challenges will definitely be membership drifting.

Some respondents from the Pentecostals said the strategies for the improvement can be that those pastors should start thinking about how to collaborate with other faith-based organization, advocacy for religious freedom and security measures. They also talked about developing a sustainable funding model. Encouraging discipleship and stewardship of financial literacy among congregational members will be of immense advantage. While some set of pastors should always give themselves to personal retreats where they will have a lot of time to commune with God, and address their challenges and that of the members in the presence of God.

Concluding Remarks

The study examined the challenges of pastoral ministry in Nigeria and some strategies for its improvement. The study really revealed that pastoral ministry in Nigeria is challenging, and these challenges partly come from the pastors themselves, the community or society where pastors are serving and their church members as well. Pastors should try to strife with all their strength in other to be relevant, well equipped, and brilliantly handles the assignment given to them and fulfill it.

In conclusion, challenges will definitely come, and pastors are the foremost recipient of such challenges, so pastors should be getting ready to face whatever challenge that is coming towards them, they should also be in deeper relationship with God so that when challenges are coming, God would have revealed to them to prepare well. On the part of their own preparedness, pastors should be well educated so that members of the church will not look down on them, and they will be able to stand and speak wherever they found themselves. Pastors should also be full of prayers because the enemy is outside prowling to seek whom to devour, that is the more reason pastors should be equipped with serious prayers.

Recommendations

Here are the recommendations to this paper:

1. There should be exploration of Nigerian cultural practices on pastoral ministry (e.g. syncretism, religious pluralism), etc.
2. Analysis of impact of poverty and economic instability on church growth and pastoral effectiveness should henceforth be taken seriously.
3. Educational wise, there should be investigation of the gaps in theological education, and training of pastors in Nigeria. There should be curricula enhancement in all theological institutions.
4. On political and social issues, there needs to be intensive discussions on how political instability and social unrest affects pastoral work negatively, and affirms what strategies to adopt in minimizing them.
5. There should be encouragement to churches in engaging in community development initiatives.
6. Proposition of leadership development programs for pastors on quarterly basis.
7. The use of technology and its importance for outreach and training should be tenaciously handled for pastors.
8. There should be formation of alliances among different denominations for mutual support against evil of the day, especially in Nigeria of today that banditry; kidnapping and genocide are the order of the day.

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